

Deliverable 1.1: Dissemination Strategy

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Work Package 1

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Executive Summary

The Dissemination Strategy serves as a comprehensive framework outlining the target audiences to be engaged, the methods and channels for engagement, and the timing and processes for dissemination at the partnership, Work Package, and partner levels.

This strategy provides practical tools, best practices, and guidelines for effective dissemination and communication related to EURAD-2. It also defines the partnership's visual identity to ensure a cohesive and recognisable presence.

This document formalises the dissemination and communication of EURAD-2 progresses and results by describing:

- How we plan to maximise EURAD-2 ambitions and expected impacts towards the potential users;
- How we raise awareness of EURAD-2 and its WPs' activities and results and the value this will bring to all the relevant stakeholders and decision and policy makers in the field of radioactive waste management;
- How we promote the exploitation of EURAD-2 results to further guide R&D policies, strategies and activities in the scientific & technical domains.

The Dissemination and Communication Strategy is done by a threefold approach of making results and knowledge available (dissemination), promoting WPs' results and EURAD-2 Partnership in general (communication) and engaging stakeholders (collaboration, end-user engagement).

Change log

- Addition of a reference to the guide on prioritisation of emails (Chapter 4.2.1)
- Inclusion of paragraphs to clarify procedure and cost eligibility for dissemination and communication activities (Chapter 6)
- Editorial changes

Keywords

Target audiences, engagement methods, best practices, end user engagement, exploitation of results, raise awareness

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Glossary

APC: Article Processing Charge

DG ENER: Directorate General for Energy

DG RTD: Directorate General for Research and Innovation

EC: European Commission

ENEF: European Nuclear Energy Forum

ERDO: European Repository Development Organisation

ETSON: European Technical Safety Organisations Network

EU: European Union

EUG: End-User Group

IAEA: International Atomic Energy Agency

ICONE: International Conference on Nuclear Engineering

IGD-TP: Implementing Geological Disposal Technology Platform

JRC: Joint Research Centre

KM: Knowledge Management

NGO: Non-Governmental Organisation

NUGENIA: Nuclear GENERation II & III Association

OECD/NEA: Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development / Nuclear Energy Agency

PMO: Programme Management Office

RD&D: Research, Development and Demonstration

RE: Research Entities

RWM: Radioactive Waste Management

SITEX: Sustainable network of Independent Technical Expertise on radioactive waste management

SNETP: Sustainable Nuclear Energy Technology Platform

SRA: Strategic Research Agenda

TSO: Technical Safety Organisation

WENRA: Western European Nuclear Regulators Association (WENRA)

WMO: Waste Management Organisation

WP: Work Package

1. Introduction

The dissemination obligations are presented and described in the EURAD-2 Grant Agreement (n°101166718), see also Figure 1 – Contractual obligations for dissemination and communication.

The dissemination obligations concern the requirement to publicly disclose the results from the partnership, typically associated with scientific activities to make research findings and results accessible and widely known but are also extended to promoting the partnership to a wider audience, thereby going beyond the partnership's own community:

“Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) [...] in a strategic, coherent and effective manner.”

Another important goal is related to the use (exploitation) of the results of which the dissemination strategy is a prerequisite for the exploitation plans developed during and after the project.

By signing the Grant Agreement, EURAD-2 participants have agreed to:

- **Promote the action and its results**, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in a strategic and effective manner
- **Disseminate results** — as soon as feasible — in a publicly available format
- **Ensure open access** (free of charge, online access for any user) to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results
- **Take measures aiming to ensure ‘exploitation’ of the results** — up to four years after the end of the project – by using them in further research activities; developing, creating or marketing a product or process; creating and providing a service, or using them in standardisation activities
- **Acknowledge EU funding and display the European flag** in all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities (including IPR protection and standards) as well as on all equipment, infrastructure and major results financed by the action by using the wording and criteria specified in the Grant Agreement (Article 17)

Figure 1 – Contractual obligations for dissemination and communication

1.1 Purpose and scope

The purpose of the EURAD-2 Dissemination Strategy is to establish and agree upon the strategic approach for communication and dissemination about EURAD-2 at programme level, at project (Work Package) level and at partner level for the whole duration of the partnership.

Since there are numerous overlaps between communication and dissemination in terms of target audiences, key-messages to convey, channels, tools and activities, it is proposed that one single strategy plan covers both communication and dissemination approaches.

This deliverable aims to formalise the dissemination and communication of EURAD-2's progresses and results by describing:

- How we plan to maximise EURAD-2 ambitions and expected impacts towards the potential users;
- How we raise awareness of the partnership and its WPs' activities and results and the value this will bring to all the relevant stakeholders and decision and policy makers in the field of radioactive waste management;

¹ EURAD-2 Grant Agreement n°101166718

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- How we promote the exploitation of EURAD-2 results to further guide R&D policies, strategies and activities in the scientific & technical domains.

Communication and dissemination in EURAD-2 shall pave the way for an effective exploitation of results and findings for participant organisations and key stakeholders.

The dissemination objective in EURAD-2 is to make results and knowledge easily available to the identified target groups, enabling stakeholders to use the results in their own work. This is achieved by enabling open access to scientific publications, sharing deliverables and outputs.

The Dissemination and Communication Strategy is done by a threefold approach of making results and knowledge available (dissemination), promoting WPs' results and EURAD-2 programme in general (communication) and engaging stakeholders (collaboration, end-user engagement).

The key-mechanism for exploitation of the results is based on EURAD-2 as a facilitator for the different participant organisations to generate the value that they exploit:

- EURAD-2 contributing by developing and making available knowledge, promoting common understanding with respect to decision-making and policy amongst actors across Europe, promoting mobile cross-European expertise, and providing guidance on how to implement R&D programmes and knowledge management;
- National decision-makers making use of EURAD-2 results for avoiding unnecessary delay in establishing and implementing the required policy;
- Industry and other involved actors to implement science and technology in a safe and cost-effective manner, making use of knowledge and expertise available across Europe and worldwide.

This deliverable will be updated as necessary during the implementation of the programme, as Beneficiaries are required to report periodically to the European Commission the concrete dissemination and exploitation activities carried out.

1.2 General requirements

All communication and dissemination activities must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag and the following funding statement: “**Co-funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement n°101166718.**”

A specific document about EU emblem in the context of European Partnerships is available in Appendix.

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

2. Target audiences

The target groups for EURAD-2 dissemination and communication activities are:

- **Radioactive Waste Management Community**

Professionals (experts, early career scientists/ engineers, students in PhD) working in:

- Waste Management Organisations (WMO) whose mission covers the management disposal of radioactive waste
- Technical Safety Organisations (TSO) and other organisations fulfilling an expertise function, carrying out activities aimed at providing the technical and scientific basis for notably supporting the decisions made by a national regulatory body
 - Nationally funded Research entities (RE) which are involved in RD&D in RWM
 - Regulators
 - Waste Owners/Generators
- **Civil Society Organisations**

- Local, national, European NGOs who are involved in RWM activities at the EU, national or local level.
- **National Policy and Decision-makers:**
 - Programme Owners
 - Usually ministries, national/regional authorities or private organisations in charge of setting-up and thereafter administrating the national programme for RWM.
- **European Commission**
 - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD)
 - Directorate-General for Energy (DG ENER)
 - Directorate-General Joint Research Centre (DG JRC)
- **International organisations / Multinational working group**
 - International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)
 - Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development – Nuclear Energy Agency (OECD/NEA)
 - European Repository Development Organisation (ERDO)
 - Western European Nuclear Regulators Association (WENRA)
 - European Technical Safety Organisations Network (ETSON)
 - Others
- **Other EU projects;**
- **Broad academia and research sector;**
- **Industry;**
- **Public at large;**
- **Media.**

3. Expected impacts

EURAD-2 addresses more than 2,300,000 m³ of radioactive waste inventory across European Union Member States, with a holistic approach covering the entire waste management cycle. The programme strives to have impacts that cover surface, shallow and deep geological disposal facilities, as well as pre-disposal including interim storage practices to provide Member States with better technologies and tools to demonstrate advancing safe waste management practices. This also includes aspects of sustainability, through use of better materials having a lower environmental footprint and supporting the waste hierarchy of avoiding and reduce radioactive waste streams.

As a co-funded European partnership, the programme must aim to assist Member States in reaching their RD&D requirements as implied by the Council Directive 2011/70/Euratom (Waste Directive), while offering optimal value for money and by creating measurable impact.

The partnership’s impacts are guided by the six drivers, as established in the EURAD(-1) 2023 SRA, which are to: implement safe long-term waste management solutions, develop tailored solutions, gain scientific insight, support innovation for optimization, enhance societal engagement and build a strong and robust knowledge management. Each of these is further explained in the table below.

Driver Shorthand	Driver Explanation
Implementation Safety	Contributing to the safe construction, operation and closure of deep geological repositories (and other disposal facilities), ensuring long-term safety.

² Report from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament on progress of implementation of Council Directive 2011/70/Euratom and an inventory of radioactive waste and spent fuel present in the Community's territory and the future prospects, 22 May 2024, COM(2024) 197 final

Tailored Solutions	<p>Supporting the development of tailored solutions for the management of various radioactive waste types in Europe:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working together on scientific, technical, managerial, societal and regulatory issues of common interest and considering the full range of potential disposal solutions and waste groups accounting for IAEA's graded approach and taking economic aspects into consideration. • Increasing robustness of approaches by addressing cross-correlations, path dependencies and potential pitfalls in the RWM strategy.
Scientific Insight	<p>Advancing state of the art science in waste management and disposal throughout the waste management chain:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploratory research in areas with significant uncertainty or in areas with high potential to improve knowledge.
Innovation for Optimisation	<p>Supporting RWM innovation for optimisation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuously managing uncertainty, improving robustness, reducing complexity, costs and other resources and optimising RWM routes and advancing technology and solutions to meet the needs of Member States.
Societal Engagement	<p>Helping to engage with and maintain mutual trust with stakeholders, and awareness in RWM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fostering transparency and fruitful interactions with Civil Society along the different phases of a RWM programme.
Knowledge Management	<p>Enhancing knowledge management and transfer between organisations, Member States and generations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Capturing, maintaining, and efficiently developing skills, knowledge and infrastructure, in view of the long lead-times and the intergenerational dimension associated to RWM.

4. Dissemination and communication channels

A wide range of activities, channels and tools can be used specifically or commonly for communication and dissemination purposes. The different activities/channels/tools are listed and briefly described in Section 4.2. Section 4.3, providing for each activity/channel/tool indications whether it serves dissemination and/or communication and/or exploitation purposes and which targeted audience they are suitable for.

4.1 General rules about dissemination and communication

4.1.1 Alignment with EURAD-2 Vision

All communication activities should align with the values, mission, and vision of EURAD-2³. Special attention is required when communicating on public platforms, such as social media, to ensure that the content remains respectful and professional. It is essential to avoid language or content that could be perceived as offensive, discriminatory, or inconsistent with the goals of the Partnership.

4.1.2 Use of Pictures

Prior to collecting, reproducing, or using images of participants for dissemination purposes—such as in publications, on websites, social media platforms, or other formats—explicit written consent must be obtained. This consent may be secured through a dedicated authorisation form signed by participants before the event or integrated into the event registration form. Social Media Communication

³ <https://www.ejp-eurad.eu/eurad-vision>

Social media content must always reflect EURAD-2's values. Caution should be exercised to ensure that no sensitive or confidential information is shared on public platforms.

4.1.3 Monitoring and Responsibility

All communication should be monitored to ensure it adheres to these guidelines. Those responsible for dissemination must seek guidance from the Coordinator whenever there is uncertainty regarding appropriate communication practices.

4.2 Communication & dissemination activities, channels and tools

4.2.1 Internal communication within the partnership

Internal communication means communication among the EURAD-2 partners. Such communication may include updates (on research performed, status of deliverables, etc.), questions, remarks, etc.

EURAD-2 partners are encouraged to communicate regularly with each other, especially within each of the respective Work Packages, in order to foster discussion and to ensure good project progress. Internal communication may be performed by face-to-face meetings, phone, email, ProjectPlace, video conference, etc.

ProjectPlace is a web-based project management tool (Extranet) which provides secure document storage and sharing.

For coordination and management issues, electronic mail is the regular way of communication. Considering the number of partners, the recipients must be selected carefully. Using email attachments should be avoided whenever possible and replaced by providing ProjectPlace links to the related files. Two generic addresses are available to reach the Programme Management Office members and the Bureau members. Contact details of members of each Consortium body will be regularly updated by the Coordinator.

A guide for the prioritisation of emails is available⁴ and defines a standardised email prioritisation system, subject line structure and notice to improve clarity, response times and information management. This approach is piloted by the Programme Management Office for the first half of 2026 and, if effective will be extended to the full Consortium in autumn 2026.

4.2.2 EURAD-2 events

- Annual Events

A total of six Annual Events will be organised throughout the course of the partnership in order to communicate EURAD-2 goals and expected impacts, to disseminate EURAD-2 activities, findings and results, as well as to exchange ideas, challenges and approaches. Annual Events shall also be a forum for exchanging the scientific and technical basis, the objectives, scope, work planning and achievements with civil society organisations and their representatives.

Within EURAD-2, the plan is to organise six Annual Events as follows:

- **Kick-off Event** shall be organised at month 1
- **First Annual Event** shall be organised between month 11 and month 14;
- **Second Annual Event** shall be organised between month 23 and month 26;
- **Third Annual Event** shall be organised between month 35 and month 38;
- **Fourth Annual Event** shall be organised between month 47 and month 50;
- **Final Annual Event** shall be organised between month 59 and month 60.

⁴ https://andra-fr.projectplace.com/external/project_report/0/11ab935942ac499cbe5b5ec83028b92d

The Annual Events are open to all target audiences as identified in Section 2, with a dedicated session to PhD and Postdocs in order to target the young scientific audience. These events shall be announced on the EURAD-2 website as well as through specific e-mailing and social media when appropriate.

- Trainings

EURAD-2 Knowledge Management (KM) Work Package will develop a diverse portfolio of tailored basic and specialised training courses under the umbrella of a “School of Radioactive Waste Management” and a training mobility programme, taking stock of and building upon already existing initiatives (i.e. past EC projects, IAEA and NEA) and creating new initiatives to bridge identified gaps. The end-users of these trainings are defined as professionals and potential new professionals at graduated and post-graduated level from EU and non-EU countries, and in particular the next generation of experts. EURAD-2 trainings and mobility programme are strong channels to disseminate results that emerge throughout EURAD-2 Work Packages in a targeted manner.

- Lunch-and-learn sessions / webinars

EURAD-2 will organise online webinars. These informal, free meetings will be open to everyone. The topics of these sessions may include sharing best practices, technical deep dives, updates on National programmes or Colleges initiatives / activities, and presentations by invited external speakers (e.g. IAEA, OECD/NEA, ...)

Depending on the type of webinar, the PMO altogether with the KM Work Package will take responsibility for organising these webinars. Communication about the events will be managed through the School of RWM website, the EURAD-2 website and social media channels. To ensure broad participation, reminder emails will be sent to EURAD-2 participants shortly before each session.

4.2.3 Participation to external events/conferences/workshops

Personal contacts and presentations through attendance at relevant workshops, conferences, and events are important channels for the dissemination of EURAD-2 results. Networking remains a crucial way to exchange, give information about the partnership and its Work Packages and keep informed about the latest developments and outcomes. Further guidance on participation to external events is available in the D1.2 Quality Management Plan.

This shall be done through:

- Presenting EURAD-2 results and achievements at scientific conferences/ workshops /forums addressing the scientific expert community;
- Presenting EURAD-2 objectives, scope, work programme and main achievements at events where broader stakeholder community and/or decision-makers are present, with the aim of providing confidence in the scientific and technical basis and enhancing awareness of the well-founded progress in the field and its time-horizons;
- Presenting and promoting EURAD-2 goals and results within the broader context at events of inter-European and international platforms, organisations:
 - Implementing Geological Disposal Technology Platform (IGD-TP);
- Sustainable network of Independent Technical Expertise on radioactive waste management (SITEX.Network);
 - EURADSCIENCE
 - Nuclear GENERation II & III Association (NUGENIA);
- IAEA International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA)
 - Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development – Nuclear Energy Agency (OECD/NEA)
- European Repository Development Organisation (ERDO)
- Exchanging the scientific-technical basis, objectives, scope, work plan and achievements with civil society and their representatives, resulting in out-reach beyond the institutional expert

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community to these key actors for advancement of national programmes and for policy decision making.

- Etc

A table showing all events of interest in the coming months/years and planned EURAD-2 participations is managed and updated by the Programme Management Office. This shared table should help to have at least one EURAD-2 contribution in each relevant event and to better structure the dissemination at the programme level.

A non-exhaustive list of external events includes, for instance:

- Annual Waste Management (WM) Symposia, Arizona, USA
- Conference on Clays in natural and engineered barriers for radioactive waste confinement (Clay conference)
- EURADWASTE conference
- European Nuclear Energy Forum (ENEF)
- IGD-TP events (Exchange Forum, etc.)
- International Conference on Nuclear Engineering (ICONE)
- IAEA Events
- OECD/NEA events
- SNETP / NUGENIA events
- SITEX events
- National and local events
- Etc.

4.2.4 EURAD website

The EURAD-2 website www.ejp-eurad.eu provides initial information on EURAD-2 Vision, Roadmap, Strategic Research Agenda, implementation (WPs), EURAD participants for a wide audience, publications and news. The website is regularly updated with on-going activities, public reports/deliverables, publications, upcoming events (internal and external to the Consortium). It also contains a dedicated End-User group page and a link to the EURADSchool website which gather all information about trainings and mobility.

The EURAD-2 website is designed to be informative with clear language to ensure wide communication with all categories of stakeholders and a wide audience. The website is administered by the Coordinator (Andra) with inputs from the Programme Management Office, Work Package Leaders and Participants.

Each Work Package shall contribute to feed the EURAD-2 website with news about their Work Package (issue of an important deliverable, reach of an important milestone, training/event related to the WP).

4.2.5 School of Radioactive Waste Management website

The School of RWM website <https://euradschool.eu/> aims to collect and organize all information concerning training and mobility. It will become a centralized place where people, both inside and outside of EURAD-2, can find all relevant information on training courses organised within EURAD-2 as well as by external partners, the EURAD-2 Mobility Programme, the EURAD-2 PhD Community and EURAD-2 webinars. It also includes a discussion forum to help connect people in the field of radioactive waste management. This way, this website aims to facilitate the formation of a tight EURAD-2 Community.

This website is administered by the KM Work Package.

4.2.6 Other websites

- Partners' websites

EURAD participant organisations are encouraged to provide EURAD-2 related information on their own website and to provide a link towards the official EURAD-2 website.

- IGD-TP, SITEX and EURADSCIENCE websites

Some information, news and announcements can also be relayed through IGD-TP, SITEX and EURADSCIENCE websites.

4.2.7 Scientific peer-reviewed publications – open access

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each EURAD-2 participant organisation must as soon as feasible disseminate its results by disclosing them by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications.

Peer-reviewed scientific open access publications in internationally recognized scientific journals (see non-exhaustive list below):

- Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering;
- Journal of Computational Physics;
- Sedimentary Geology;
- Journal of Nuclear Materials;
- Science of Total Environment;
- Electrochimica Acta;
- Materials chemistry and Physics;
- Applied Clay Science;
- Engineering Geology;
- Journal of Geochemical Exploration;
- International Journal of Geomechanics;
- Journal of Chemical & Engineering Data;
- International journal of rock mechanics and mining sciences;
- Environmental Science & Technology;
- Applied Geochemistry;
- Physics and Chemistry of the Earth;
- Journal of Hydrology;
- Environmental Modelling & Software;
- Journal of Geosciences;
- Journal of Hazardous Materials;
- Computers and Geotechnics;
- Etc.

The European Commission promotes the overall concept of Open Research by supporting open access in its framework programmes, aiming to improve science and innovation in the public and private sectors. By making project results and data accessible to all societal actors, other researchers, innovators and the public, they can find and re-use these for their own specific needs. In this way further research is encouraged, novel solutions can be found, and complex challenges can be tackled.

Each Beneficiary must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to results of the project. It is not, however, an obligation to publish and does not override any prior decisions to seek IP protection.

- Self-Archiving > GREEN Open Access

The final peer-reviewed publication is saved in an online repository of choice, often after an embargo period set by the publisher. Beneficiaries must ensure open access to the publication within a maximum of six months (twelve months in the social sciences and humanities).

- Open Access Publishing > GOLD Open Access

Publication in Open Access journals. Open access to the peer-reviewed publication is provided immediately, often by paying a fee to the publisher. Note that a copy of the publication still needs to be deposited in a repository.

Open access costs are eligible for funding, if they fulfil the general eligibility conditions specified in the Grant Agreement.

- HYBRID Open Access

Open access to the article published in subscription journal provided by journal's article processing charge (APC).

4.2.8 EURAD-2 newsletter

A quarterly newsletter is published on the website and sent to EURAD-2 dissemination contact list and aims to keep all interested parties informed on the activities and findings of EURAD, including technical projects (Work Packages), past and upcoming events, publications, etc. The Coordinator is responsible for producing the newsletter, seeking inputs from the WPs and wider community.

4.2.9 Social networks

Social media allow to reach a wide — but also targeted — audience and can be used for both communication and dissemination purposes. EURAD-2 shall use Twitter and LinkedIn social media. The EURAD-2 Twitter and LinkedIn accounts shall be administrated by Andra, as Coordinator. EURAD-2 contributors are also encouraged to tweet/post using relevant hashtags such as #EURAD-2, #radioactivewaste, #geologicaldisposal, #EURATOM, #Horizon2020, #EUcollaboration etc.

XTweet posts shall be used to share short comments (+ photos, URL) about publication of a deliverable, EURAD-2 events/workshops that can instantaneously reach a large audience or retweet any content of interest for EURAD community. The X account is retained for now but is no longer used for publishing news.

- LinkedIn

LinkedIn shall be used as a networking tool to interact with individuals (professionals)/groups and to share and disseminate information about EURAD-2 results, events, relevant information.

4.2.10 Press releases

A series of press releases to be published in local newspapers, as well as in specialised magazines and online media is envisaged. They shall be used to announce important news about EURAD-2, and will be quality control checked by the Coordinator.

4.2.11 Information material

Communication tools, such as flyers, brochures, posters, rollups, synthesis, videos etc. that may be displayed and/or distributed during workshops, conferences or congresses, and/or published on EURAD-2 website shall also be developed to support any communication/dissemination activities.

A communication kit containing a set of slides introducing EURAD-2, a brochure and a background for video meeting is available for internal and external communication on ProjectPlace.

4.3 Channels/tools/activities vs. Target audiences

The table below provides an overview of the planned activities for dissemination and/or communication. These are targeted to reach different audiences in the technical community and the public with more general-interest views.

Dissemination type	Location	Time	Audience	Reach
Annual project event (WP1)	Around Europe	M12, M24, M36, M48, M58	Participants, EUG, stakeholders	300 persons
Project Newsletters (WP1)	Project web page	4 / year	All interested parties	1000 persons
100+ scientific journal publications	i.e. Journals of: Waste Management, Nuclear Engineering and Design, Nuclear Energy Science & Power Generation Technology, etc.)	M12 – M60 + 2 years (2025-2031)	Technical experts	1000 persons
200+ scientific conference presentations / posters	i.e. International Conferences on Safety of RWM, WM Symposium (USA), Nuclear Decommissioning and Remediation Conference, etc.)	M12 – M60 + 2 years (2025-2031)	Technical experts	5000 persons
Summaries in international policy forums	Worldwide (European Commission media such as Cordis News, IAEA and NEA events and news)	Annually	All interested parties	5000 persons
Summaries at EC/Colleges organised events (all WPs)	IGD-TP Forum, SNETP Forum, EURADWASTE2025, Europe	Annually	Experts, EUG stakeholders, industry	1000 persons

The dissemination impact indicators will be based on tracking the following metrics, as also described earlier by KPIs:

- number and diversity (country, institute) of participants to project events and seminars,
- number of visitors to web page,
- number of subscribers to newsletter, blog and webcasts,
- number of references in scientific publications.

5. Visual identity

The following sections give instruction on the visual identify of various aspects used during communication and dissemination of the partnership.

5.1 EURAD-2 logo

Logo

5.2 Colours

Within visual identify of EURAD-2, primary colours should be used whenever possible. Secondary colours are used when the use of primary colour detracts from readability of the document.

Primary colours

Secondary colours

5.3 Pictograms

5.4 Official presentation template

5.5 Poster template

5.6 Word template

6. Follow-up of dissemination / communication activities

All communication / dissemination activities performed within the partnership shall be regularly reported to EURAD-2 General Assembly and to the European Commission. These activities form an integral part of the annual reporting showing impact of the partnership and outreach to the wider community. Their documentation is also necessary for the justification of reimbursable costs by the partners.

WP Boards must be informed of and validate any submission related to their respective Work Package (e.g., poster, abstract, presentation, or article). Once a submission is accepted for a workshop, event, or conference, the WP Leader shall inform the Secretariat to ensure proper tracking of project representation across events. The dissemination materials must be shared with the secretariat (secretariat@ejp-eurad.eu) via ProjectPlace (or by email) to ensure an accurate and complete record of all documents.

All dissemination materials must include appropriate acknowledgment of the European Commission's funding (see 1.2). Costs linked to submissions or materials that do not include this acknowledgment will not be eligible in the financial report.

According to the Grant Agreement, the travels for which costs are claimed must be necessary for the action. Travel costs related to an event at which the partner carried out work that was not specifically related to the action are not eligible.

A follow-up table for dissemination is regularly updated and available for EURAD-2 participant organisations on ProjectPlace, and is utilised for annual reporting to the EC.

Dissemination activity name	Type of dissemination	Target audience reached													Description of the objectives with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	
		Industry, Business partners	Innovators	EU institutions	National authorities	Regional authorities	Local authorities	Civil society	Citizens	Research communities	Specific end-user communities	International organisations (UN body, OECD, etc.)	Other	Investors			

A follow-up table for communication activities is regularly updated and available for EURAD-2 participant organisations on ProjectPlace. and is utilized for annual reporting to the EC.

Communication activity name	Description	Target audience	Communication channel	Outcome / KPI	Status

Appendix A. The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU Partnerships

The European Union (EU) has numerous funding programmes, which support projects and initiatives in various domains across the EU and beyond.

All beneficiaries, managing authorities and implementing partners of EU funding must use the EU emblem in their communication to acknowledge the support received under EU programmes and contribute to the visibility of the EU on the ground.

Recipients of EU funding have a general obligation to communicate and raise EU visibility. An important obligation in this context is the correct and prominent display of the EU emblem, in combination with a simple funding statement, mentioning the EU support. Due to the different legal nature of all 52 EU Partnerships, there is no one-size-fits-all approach.

The following guidelines contain instructions for the use of EU Partnerships. It provides information and examples on the placement of the EU emblem and funding statement.

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I. Visual guidelines

The **EU emblem** is the single most important visual brand used to acknowledge the origin and ensure **the visibility of EU funding**. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight EU support⁽¹⁾.

The ready-to-use EU emblem including the funding statement can be downloaded in all EU languages, Arabic, Icelandic, Norwegian, Turkish and Russian from the European Commission's webpage: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/information/logos_downloadcenter

The use of the EU emblem

- Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars and information material such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc. in electronic form via traditional or social media), as well as any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant, must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate).

What does the 'prominent display' of the EU emblem mean?

Recipients of EU funding have the obligation to ensure that the EU emblem can easily be seen in a given context. This context might vary and depends on many factors. Due attention needs to be given, for example, to the emblem's size, positioning, colour and quality relative to its context.

Recipients of EU funding must be able to demonstrate and explain how they ensure prominence for the EU emblem and the accompanying funding statement at all stages of a programme, project or partnership⁽²⁾.

- The European Union emblem must not be modified or merged with any other graphic element or text. If other logos are displayed in addition to the EU emblem, the latter must be at least the same size as the biggest of the other logos. Apart from the EU emblem, no other visual identity or logo can be used to highlight the EU support.

1. A few limited exceptions in some programmes exist – these are defined in the legal bases of the respective programmes.

2. Please note that some EU programmes foresee more specific obligations in the programme's legal basis or financing agreement.

Technical characteristics

- The statement 'Funded by the European Union' or 'Co-funded by the European Union' must always be spelled out in full and placed next to the emblem. It should be translated into local languages, where appropriate.
- The typeface to be used in conjunction with the EU emblem must stay simple and easily readable. The recommended typefaces are Arial and Myriad Pro. Other tolerated fonts are Auto, Calibri, Garamond, Tahoma, Trebuchet, Ubuntu and Verdana.
- Underlining and use of other font effects is not allowed.
- The positioning of the text in relation to the EU emblem must not interfere with the EU emblem in any way. The positioning of the funding statement in relation to the EU emblem is described in these guidelines.
- The colour of the font should be Reflex Blue (the same blue colour as the European flag), white or black depending on the background.
- The font size used should be proportionate to the size of the emblem.
- Sufficient contrast should be ensured between the EU emblem and the background. If there is no alternative to a coloured background, a white border must be placed around the flag, with the width of this being equal to one 25th of the height of the rectangle.
- Where several operations are taking place at the same location and are supported by the same or different funding instruments, or where further funding is provided for the same operation at a later date, only one plaque or billboard must be displayed^[3].

Graphics guide to the European flag (emblem)

https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en

³. This applies to shared management programmes governed by the common provisions regulation, Regulation (EU) No 1303/2013.

There are 2 options to highlight the Partnership:

1. In the case of a “funded” or “co-funded” EU Partnership.
2. In the case of an EU Partnership that has no funding/co-funding from the EU.

1. “Funded” or “Co-funded” EU Partnership

Use the **association of the EU emblem with the funding statement**

Funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by
the European Union

together with the wording **“European Partnership”**

For the use of the association of the EU emblem with the funding statement, refer to these guidelines:
https://commission.europa.eu/resources-partners/european-commission-visual-identity_en

Rules for the use of the “European Partnership” wording are explained in the following pages.

2. Not funded/co-funded EU Partnership

Use the wording **“European Partnership” together with the European flag (emblem)**

Rules for the use of the “European Partnership” wording are explained in the following pages.

Graphics guide to the European flag (emblem)

https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en

ATTENTION

Never place the EU emblem (flag) twice on a page

Do not combine the EU emblem/funding statement, an additional EU emblem (flag) and European Partnership on the same page.

The only exceptions are for web pages: you may have the EU emblem together with European Partnership at the top and the the EU emblem/funding statement at the bottom of the page.

Use of the “European Partnership” wording

Font

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP **European Partnership**

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP **European Partnership**

The proposed fonts for the European Partnership is either **Arial** or **Myriad Pro**. It offers a simple and neutral style and are available for all EU languages. Arial is one of the pre-installed fonts by Microsoft and Adobe software, so it is easily accessible for everyone. Myriad Pro is accessible on the Adobe Creative Cloud. The other tolerated fonts are Auto, Calibri, Garamond, Tahoma, Trebuchet, Ubuntu and Verdana.

European Partnership can be **written all in caps** (preferred version) **or in both caps and lower caps**.

The space between the letters should be 25.

Arial

The recommended weight is Bold. Regular can also be used.

European Partnership
EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP
 The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog
THE QUICK BROWN FOX JUMPS OVER THE LAZY DOG 1234567890

European Partnership
EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP
 The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog
THE QUICK BROWN FOX JUMPS OVER THE LAZY DOG 1234567890

Myriad Pro

The recommended weight is Bold. Semi Bold and Regular can also be used.

European Partnership
EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP
 The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog
THE QUICK BROWN FOX JUMPS OVER THE LAZY DOG 1234567890

European Partnership
EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP
 The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog
THE QUICK BROWN FOX JUMPS OVER THE LAZY DOG 1234567890

European Partnership
EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP
 The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog
THE QUICK BROWN FOX JUMPS OVER THE LAZY DOG 1234567890

Horizontal options

European Partnership should be written in **one line**, with a **tracking of 25**.

Vertical options

European Partnership should be written in **two lines**, always with a **centered alignment**, a **tracking of 25** and a **leading 1 or 2pt more than the body of the font**.

Colours

The **European Partnership wording** and the **association of the EU emblem with the funding statement** can be used in their **negative version** if needed. In this case European Partnership is written in white. (Refer to its guidelines: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf)

Protection area

The protection area must remain free of competing texts, logos, images or any other visual element that could compromise its good legibility.

As the European Partnership wording is always combined with an EU flag on the same page, the protection area around it is based on the space between the center of the right star and the right border of the flag.

Minimum size

The **size of the font** should be **proportional to the size of the funding statement** or the **EU emblem** that will figure on the same page.

The minimum height of the EU emblem must be 1cm. In that case, **the minimum size of font** for the wording European Partnership should be **10pt**.

When using the EU funding statement in a small size, we highly recommend using the horizontal version, with the bold weight.

How to place your organisation’s logo alongside the EU emblem, the funding statement and ‘European Partnership’ wording on communication material

When displayed alongside the partner organisation’s logo, the EU emblem and the ‘European Partnership’ wording must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the partner organisation’s logo.

The placement of the EU emblem should not give the impression that the partner is connected in any way to the EU institutions. It is therefore recommended to **place the EU emblem at a distance from the partner organisation’s logo**.

The European Partnership wording is not a logo and should not be considered as such. This is why the choice of font, case and weight is flexible. This flexibility also allows to better integrate the wording in the Partner visual identity. The placement of the wording is also important so that it does not appear as a logo. Respect the minimum protection area around the text.

As much as possible, do not place the European Partnership wording too close to the EU emblem so it remains a statement.

The European Partnership wording can be placed either left or right to the EU emblem or the funding statement depending on the design of the page. It should be **aligned to the middle of the EU emblem in the height**. (not aligned to the bottom or top of it)

REMINDER

Never place the EU emblem (flag) twice on a page: do not combine the EU emblem/funding statement, an additional EU emblem (flag) and European Partnership on the same page.

The only exceptions are for web pages: you may have the EU emblem together with European Partnership at the top and the the EU emblem/funding statement at the bottom of the page.

1. “Funded” or “Co-funded” EU Partnership examples

The placement of the **EU emblem** and the **European Partnership** wording will depend on the design of the communication material, such as printed or digital products or websites and their mobile version.

Webpage exception:

two EU emblems on the same page so that the EU is well visible on the top, and well visible when scrolling down the page.

2. Not funded/co-funded EU Partnership examples

II. Administrative agreement with the Council of Europe regarding the use of the EU emblem by third parties

(Official Journal of the European Union C 271 of 8 September 2012)

General principle

Any natural or legal person ("user") may use the EU emblem or any of its elements, subject to the following conditions of use.

Conditions of use

The use of the EU emblem and/or any of its elements is allowed, irrespective of whether the use is of a non-profit or a commercial nature, unless:

- the use creates the incorrect impression or assumption that there is a connection between the user and any of the institutions, bodies, offices, agencies and organs of the European Union or the Council of Europe;
- the use leads the public to erroneously believe that the user benefits from the support, sponsorship, approval or consent of any of the institutions, bodies, offices, agencies and organs of the European Union or the Council of Europe;
- the use is in connection with any objective or activity which is incompatible with the aims and principles of the European Union or of the Council of Europe, or which would otherwise be unlawful.

Trade mark and related issues

In accordance with the previously mentioned conditions, the use of the EU emblem does not mean consent to registration of the emblem or an imitation thereof as a trade mark or any other IP right. The European Commission and the Council of Europe will continue to monitor applications for registration of the EU emblem or part thereof as (part of) IP rights, in accordance with the applicable legal provisions.

Legal responsibility

Any user that intends to use the EU emblem or elements will be held legally responsible for that use. The users will be liable for any abusive use and possible prejudice following from such use under the laws of the Member States or any non-EU country applicable to them.

Right to pursue any abuse

The European Commission reserves the right to pursue on its own initiative or on request by the Council of Europe:

- any use which does not comply with the conditions set out herein or
- any use which the European Commission or the Council of Europe deem abusive in the courts of the Member States or any non-EU country.

Don'ts

Do not choose a font other than Arial or Myriad and other tolerated fonts.

~~EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP~~

Do not use any font effects.

~~European Partnership~~

Do not add other graphic elements.

 ~~EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP~~

Do not make the text disproportionately bigger or smaller compared to the EU emblem.

 ~~EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP~~

Do not use any colour other than the EU corporate blue white or black.

~~European Partnership~~

Do not modify the text proportions.

~~EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP~~

Do not write 'EU'. It must always be spelled out as 'European'.

~~EU PARTNERSHIP~~

Do not add European Partnership to the funding statement.

 Funded by ~~The European Union European Partnership~~

Do not replace the EU emblem with the European Commission logo.

 ~~Funded by the European Union~~

Do not replace the EU emblem with any other graphic element.

 ~~Funded by The European Union~~

Do not align European Partnership to the bottom or top of the EU emblem. Keep it align in the middle and well-distanced.

 ~~EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP~~

Place European Partnership well separated from the EU emblem.

 ~~EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP~~

Do not modify the EU emblem.

 ~~Funded by the European Union~~

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- any use which does not comply with the conditions set out herein or
- any use which the European Commission or the Council of Europe deem abusive in the courts of the Member States or any non-EU country.

Contact

If you have any questions regarding the use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes, please write to RTD-GRAPHIC-TEAM@ec.europa.eu.

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